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THE INTERFERENCES OF BURNOUT SYNDROME AND MOTIVATION IN THE PROFESSIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. Motivation is the mobilizing force of the person, which redirects and guides the whole behavior in the direction of satisfying the necessity, so it is responsible for focusing energy and attention on reaching the goals and gaining satisfaction from the work done. This is why, it is logical to assume that once a person has a well-founded reason and an optimum level of motivation will have a quite high performance, he will be characterized as an energetic, lively, persevering person and will take advantage of everything chance to realize his potential and objectives. However, burnout syndrome is opposed to a person's motivational state because the burnout syndrome person is emotionally exhausted, productivity is diminished, and depersonalization occurs.

Keywords: *depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, professional environment, stress, Yerkes-Dodson's Law.*

Introduction

Professional stress, in the conditions of actual society, became omnipresent and constitutes a real social problem. Stress agents are influencing the individual and produce somatic and psychological tear, that is correlated with various adaptation difficulties. Among the consequences of excessive occupational stress are emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduction of personal achievements, all of which constitute burnout syndrome [1].

Introduced by Bradley (1969), developed and developed by Freudenberger (1974) and Cristina Maslach (1976), the concept of burnout signifies *a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduction of professional achievement, occurring in individuals professionally involved with others*. The burnout syndrome has three basic components [3]:

1. Emotional exhaustion is expressed through the feeling of fatigue and emotional imbalance caused by professional work. Emotional overload and the impossibility of restoring energy interfere with self-salvage attempt by alienation. The person becomes incapable of working with the same energy. Work is done formally. Emotional exhaustion is an important indication of emotional burning.

2. Depersonalization - means lack of emotions, the presence of cynicism. Negative attitude towards the work accomplished can cause pessimism, lack of willingness to communicate, ignorant behavior.

3. The reduction of personal achievements is accompanied by a decrease in self-assessment of the person. The main manifestations of this stage are: the negative tendency of self appreciation, achievements and professional successes; the manifestation of negativity in relation to service obligations, the decrease of professional motivation, etc.

Professional motivation

Professional motivation, at the resistance stage, play a majore role in the avoidance of symptoms specific to burnout syndrome. Motivation represents the whole of the factors that trigger the activity of the individual, it guides it towards certain purposes and supports it energetically [2]. The study of professional motivation involves analyzing the factors that determine the employee's behavior and the mechanisms that explain the trigger. Under the effect of internal or external stimuli, the motives bring the individual into action and support his activity for a while, despite the obstacles that may arise. Moreover, when an employee has an objective, he makes a forecast, thus making a subjective measure of the probability of his success [4, p. 80].

Of major importance in this respect is the optimal motivation, as a way of objectively assessing the degree of difficulty of the situation; efficient management of personal resources and prevention of emotional exhaustion. Thus, in the case of excessive motivation, the individual acts in the conditions in which the energy impulse disorganizes him and makes him lose energy on small and insignificant things, even before he properly confronts the obstacle. Such situations can result in the person's energetic and emotional exhaustion, so he is no longer able to meet the requirements. On the other hand, the employee lacking motivation (intrinsic or even extrinsic) is not sufficiently involved in solving professional tasks, which can condition the failure of the working plan, conflicts with the administration and colleagues, lack of professional satisfaction, etc., which in time can also sold with emotional burning. We must also mention Yerkes-Dodson's Law, according to which, the intensity of activity ensures the performance improvement only up to the level of a critical area, then, if the intensity of motivation continues to increase, the performance begins to decrease [2, p. 215]. Professional activity (physical or intellectual) involves a permanent energy consumption, and if it involves direct interaction with other people, consumption is also emotional. When the work done is pleasant or the results are what is expected, the work itself is a true motivational source [3, p. 420]. However, in case of burnout syndrome, excessive energy consumption can not be fully restored until the next day or even during professional vacations.

Conclusions

Burnout syndrome is a complex phenomenon with a predominantly negative connotation that occurs and manifests itself in the professional environment, disturbing the entire existential sphere of the employee. Major importance in managing the employee's energy and emotional resources lies in professional motivation. Optimal motivation has a considerable influence on the prevention of burnout syndrome, helping to manage emotional exhaustion, avoiding depersonalization and reducing personal achievement in the professional environment.

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